

Eliciting An Emotional Response in Architecture

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Abstract

I wish to report on a project I ran for student architects in the Welsh School of Architecture, Cardiff University, during the academic sessions 2002-3 and 2003-4. The challenge of the project was to create an installation (in the sense of 'art gallery installation') that would elicit an emotional response in those who experience it. In each session the project was undertaken by a group of eight students, each of whom conceived, designed and built their own installation. Students were encouraged to consider the range of emotions that it might be possible to elicit through the design of architectural space, and the means available to them. The emotions they explored included: embarrassment, pride, shyness, loss, vulnerability, shock, grief, intrigue, amusement, joy, claustrophobia, exhibitionism.... The means they exploited included: enclosure, light, sound, smells, textures, reflection, movement, elevation.... The resulting installations were exhibited and experienced by a wide range of people. This paper describes the more successful installations produced by this project, and discusses the possibilities in architecture for provoking emotional responses by architectural means.

Introduction

An instance. In the closing bars of the last of Richard Strauss's *Four Last Songs*, one can see, in one's imagination, an Arthurian barque bearing a departing soul, gliding silently away through the mist across smooth water, the slight ripples in which are reflecting ethereal light. The music, left alone (the words of the song are finished), evokes a poignant affirmation of

death through a gently reciprocating cadence of emotions. Loss and resignation commingle with joy and acceptance. Beauty and softness mitigate grief and loss.

Another instance. Sitting in a supermarket car park, listening to a Beethoven 'late' string quartet, the shoppers that pass in the windscreen are transformed by the sounds into shades of humanity, burdened with mortality. Their motion slowed, their permanent cares and temporary joys, though shrouded still, become more evident.

A third instance. Driving along a motorway, listening to the 'a capella' version of Suzanne Vega's song *Tom's Diner*. A gentle empathy with the soft rhythms of the song, and an image of being in the diner and seeing the people's maybe consequential interactions, replaces the drone of engine and monotony of the view ahead.

Music deals in, and elicits, emotion. Emotional stimulation and manipulation is its principal power. Is this true of architecture too? Architecture is more concerned with practicalities, with the accommodation of uses, with the pragmatics of construction. Architecture is more concerned with the appearance of the object, with the iconic photograph, with a neat junction between parts. But the predominant focus on the pragmatics and superficialities of architecture only obscures, it does not deny its potential for eliciting emotions in those who experience it. Some might experience an emotional response to colours, odours and textures of materials: the animal soft-hardness of leather; the multi-coloured polish of marble; the honey-coloured roughness of sawn cedar; the inviting comfort of an armchair.... Most will experience some sort of emotional response to warmth, to light, to darkness, to cool air drifting through a window on a warm day, to opulence... or squalor. The grand scale of a space can evoke awe; a tightly enclosed space can provoke claustrophobia. A drawn out route might build suspense; instant exposure to apparent danger provokes shock and fear. The emotional possibilities of architecture are endless.

Architects are responsible for setting the frames within which people live. This is a significant responsibility, but student architects, for the most part, have to develop their skill using media that fall far short of replicating the experiential subtleties of the places they design. Alongside the problems students have in understanding the real characteristics of building materials and components in their 'construction' studies, overcoming their difficulty in understanding the actuality of the places they are designing is one of the substantial

challenges of architectural education. It is a challenge that is recognised but often conceded as being next-to-impossible to overcome: buildings are expensive artefacts; students must learn to design them without the possibility of being able to evaluate their proposals through experiencing them in reality; they design through the abstracting media of drawing and scale model, and the even more abstracting medium of computer drafting. The effects of this distancing of students from reality are insidious, and profoundly inform the paradigm of design they develop (and which thereafter influences their practice): conceptual issues and qualities of a design that reside in the medium through which it is presented come to dominate the experiential and tectonic character of the actual building; sensitivity to the emotional impact of real places on the psyches that experience them becomes atrophied, ignored because it is difficult to simulate in the media through which design is developed. [Some theoretically inclined architects respond by celebrating this divorce of design from reality, and declaring it intellectually valid (like decorators papering over a window by mistake and then saying they like it better like that anyway, because it challenges the orthodoxies of paper-hanging and the accepted role of ‘window’).]

Such is one of the oldest complaints about the professionalisation and abstraction of architectural design, and its removal from the actuality of building, of framing real places in real time and in real locations. Sometimes this complaint is made by protagonists of the prosaic. But it is a complaint that belongs most legitimately to those who regret the loss to architecture of experiential subtlety and poetic complexity. Just as in music (whose student composers *can* get to hear the fruits of their labour in reality), the intellectual argument for the composition of a work of architecture should surely concede supremacy to the actuality of the result [whilst also recognising that ‘the result’ (in both music and architecture) may be interpreted and experienced differently by different people, or differently by the same person on different occasions].

The project

The subject of this paper is a student project run with the intention of stimulating sensitivity to the emotional potential of architecture by requiring students to explore that potential through the concentrated form of an installation. The project was run for a group of eight students in the final year of their architectural studies at the Welsh School of Architecture in Cardiff, UK. It was intended as a ‘primer’ for their major thesis design project, which would

later occupy some six months to the end of the academic year. This 'primer' installation project was allocated approximately six weeks, during the autumn semester. During that time the students were required to conceive, design and build an installation; one each. They were however allowed to collaborate in acquiring materials and expected to help each other in constructing the installations. The ideas-generation phase of the project was also run as a group, each individual was expected to contribute ideas for discussion and to develop and crystallise their own project. The project was run on two occasions, in October-December 2002 and October-December 2003.

The installations the students created had to be full-size and real, not in the form of maquettes or drawings. For most this was, after some five years of architectural education, the first time they would make something real that would directly engage the experience of other people – 'the person'. Understandably, the students exhibited some trepidation, to which there were various dimensions. First, few of them had any direct experience of making things, so they were circumspect about possessing the skills necessary to build an installation. Second, they were worried about sourcing the materials that they would need, and whether they would be able to obtain them soon enough to be able to finish the project on time. Third, this would be the first time that one of their designs would be tested by actual experience, rather than by projected experience through interpretation of drawings, models and other sorts of visualisations. And fourth, they were reticent about producing extreme emotional responses in the people who would experience their work. They toyed with ideas of making people cry, or scream with terror, or be embarrassed by lascivious possibilities, but, despite encouragement to shock and even offend, withdrew from these extremes with typically British reserve. They replaced such extreme approaches in favour of attempting to elicit more subtle, poetic and amusing responses.

So, briefly, the project challenged the students in various ways. Intellectually it would challenge them to explore the emotional potential of places and to gear that emotional impact to as high a level as they could manage. (This was conditioned more by their sense of propriety than by any intellectual limitations.)

Selected examples of student installations

Here is a selection of the installations produced by the students on the two occasions this project was run. The chosen examples are obviously those that I, and the other students and staff involved in the project, considered to be the most stimulating and hence successful in the terms set down in the project brief and established in group discussions with the students. Some of the examples are described here only in words. These examples were either impossible to photograph, or were such that photographic depiction was irrelevant because it would fail to convey the non-visual components of the installation: vertigo, sounds, smells, textures, disorientation, shock, bemusement, movement, gravity, insecurity, and, of course, laughter. This lack of photographability is not seen as a shortcoming, but more as a virtue. The fact that an installation was impossible to photograph in a way that would convey its meaning and experience was often an indicator that the student had given priority in its conception to the sensual and emotional experience that a person using it would have, rather than just how the installation would look in a photograph or a drawing. In many cases the visually unprepossessing installations were the ones that turned out to have the most powerful emotional impact. (This subversion of the hegemony of the visual in the interests of a multi-dimensional emotional and sensual experience was another factor that unnerved the students, especially those whose success in their architectural studies to date had been due to adeptness at producing high quality presentations composed solely of visual imagery.) Where possible, however, illustrations of examples have been included here, even though these, in all cases, convey little of the sensual and emotional potency of the installations they depict. This potency I have tried to describe in words. The installations were not given names that would detract from or limit their interpretation; they are identified here by the names of their authors.

Example 1: Jill Himsworth (2002)

There is no point in showing a photograph of this installation. All one would see would be a rather large orthogonal box, some four feet (1200mm) by four feet in plan and about twelve feet (3000mm) high. In the centre of the front of the box is an opening about two feet (600mm) wide by six feet (1800mm) high, covered by a black curtain. The sill of this opening is about two feet (600mm) above the floor on which the box stands. Three simple steps invite the person to climb and enter the box through the curtained opening.

Once through the curtain the person finds him- or herself standing rather precariously on a short projecting plank, like a diving board. With the curtain drawn behind, the inside of the box is black and dark, except for a number of tiny pin-pricks of electric light (like stars) in the ceiling. As the person looks down, these 'stars' are reflected in the flat sheet of water that covers the bottom of the box. They appear to be a long way down, suggesting that the diving board is higher than anticipated. The effect is vertigo, the emotion fear.

Example 2: Amy Serafini (2002)

Another box, about eight foot (2400mm) cube, this installation is a *camera obscura* – a small room in which an image of the outside is projected through a small hole (or lens) in one side onto the opposite wall. The inside has to be dark; even so the image is feint and upside-down. Being an eight-foot cube, this 'Platonic cave' is big enough to enter and sequester oneself to watch the outside world projected upside-down and faintly on the wall. The strangeness is enhanced by music (the same Beethoven late string quartet mentioned at the beginning of this paper). The effect is not only on the person within. Students outside tend to want to entertain the prisoner by dancing and jumping within the view of the portal through which the image enters the box. The emotion elicited is thus a confusion of pathos and fun.

Example 3: Farah Ramli (2002) (Illustrated on the title page of this paper)

Not a box. This student set herself the challenge of making the person dance despite him- or herself. She built a framework within which a life size articulated puppet is suspended. By strings and pulleys the puppet's extremities are attached to those of the person, who is asked to make the puppet dance. The result is that both the puppet and the person dance, strangely reciprocating each other's movements. This was one of the strongest examples of an installation that required the person for its completion.

Example 4: Tony Ho (2002)

A box (four foot by four foot by eight foot high), open on one side, but with a floor and a ceiling. At the back of the box, strung taut and vertical, is an electric guitar string, lit from above. The string invites a tentative touch, or a pluck. The result is a gargantuan noise that shocks. The shock subsides and the person begins to feel the power of being able to create such a powerful sound with such little effort.

[The other installations produced in 2002 were: a labyrinth, in which the person was disorientated; a simpler labyrinth that was intended as a metaphor for grief; a box in which the person was exposed to an infinity (by use of mirrors) of gawping expectant faces; a catwalk; and a forest of large cardboard tubes in which the person could wander. This last one was used as a setting for a short video produced by another student in the year.]

Example 5: Sam Austin (2003) (Illustrated above)

A small room.... Four large rectangular polythene balloons were made, tailored exactly so that when they were inflated with air they would fill the room from wall to wall and from floor to false (translucent) ceiling. The person may enter the room, but, because of the balloons, can only, and with some effort, push his or her way around the wall or between the balloons. The fabric of the balloons is partly transparent, like a mist. The space of the room is still there, but trapped in the balloons and hence inaccessible to the person. The pressure of the polythene on the person is substantial, though breathing is not threatened.

Example 6: Marcelle Newbold (2003) (Illustrated above)

This installation is about memory, and how an inanimate installation can remember the person's presence once he or she has gone. To that extent the person is essential to the installation. It was intended to be a six-foot (1800mm) square vertically positioned 'field' of hundreds of short dowels that could be pushed into their holes in a large board to leave an impression. The field was to be marked with the outlines of Leonardo da Vinci's version of the Vitruvian Man, who, with arms outstretched, would fit neatly into a circumscribed circle and square. In the event a version that was more economical in material and time was needed, so a cruciform field was made instead, with outstretched arms and a projection for the head. The symbolic potency of the piece was thus radically changed. No longer a 'humanist' statement, it became an invitation to adopt the posture of a crucifixion.

Example 7: Caroline Almond (2003) (Illustrated above)

This installation consists of a large blackboard as the backdrop to an informal stage set located in a well-frequented 'nodal' point of the school of architecture; a location where there is some space, and where a number of routes meet. In front of the blackboard backdrop is provided a variety of simple furniture and domestic appliances, all painted white, and some of which is damaged. These things are in a pile, with no arrangement. The implicit invitation is that the person may arrange the things to form a place and make a cup of tea or watch television. The blackboard, provided with coloured chalks, is also an implicit invitation to the person, to fill it with graffiti. On the day of the crits, the jury arranged and used the furniture and became the completing component of the installation. They found themselves criting a piece of which they were an essential part.

[The other installations produced in 2003 were: a scaffold on which insecurity was exacerbated by the person's attempts to overcome it; a large globe in which sound was focussed back inside the person's head; a three dimensional open-work timber maze; a clutch of cylindrical black gauze tubes in which the person could feel veiled from the world; and a triangular, internally mirrored space that produced complex reflections. Some of these installations were not completed.]

Discussion

The project successfully drew attention to the emotional potential of architecture. It did this by exaggeration, by working at the extremes allowed by installation art but for which opportunities in architecture proper are more limited.

The successful eliciting of emotional responses depended on and required an empathic projection by students into the possible effects of the installations they made on the persons who experienced them. These emotional effects were not however totally predictable, and also could vary between different individual persons. A primary criterion for success was engagement. The installation had first to engage the person, and then to affect his or her emotions.

Installations that worked on more senses than merely the visual were particularly successful. The senses that the installations stimulated and played with included some of the primary

senses: sound, smell, touch. But they also stimulated and played with other senses such as: balance; exposure; shock; orientation; breathing; humour; and the sense of being in some way teased. These secondary senses either constituted or provoked the emotional responses: the fear or trepidation; the seclusion; the claustrophobia; the joy; the amusement... that were the end product, and mark of success, of the installations.

The project also reinforced the centrality of the human being to notions of place, not in pragmatic, utilitarian, functional terms, but in the sense of human response to situation, in emotional terms. Without the person as participant, the installations would have no meaning, would be incomplete, and worthless. Persons and situations were brought together in symbiotic relationships, feeding off each other, and the authors of the installations felt a sense of power and achievement as the 'puppet masters' (literally in one instance).

In this project the emotional situation was intensified. Rarely will, what one might call, an orthodox work of architecture operate with the intensity that the student installations did. But these installations still exist on the same dimension as orthodox works of architecture, and it is feasible that architects could move their focus of attention towards this more extreme end of the dimension of emotional response elicited by their work.

The issues of the project were of engagement and involvement. This involved empathy on the part of the students with the person who would experience their work. They could of course use themselves as guinea-pigs in the experiment. But their prior knowledge of the experience their installations would offer meant that their own experience might be different from those of the person coming to it unprepared and without knowledge of what was going to happen. The test of the quality of the work in these installations was not so much in the student's intention but in the effect produced.

Conclusion

Architects have sought to explore emotional responses in their work through history. It is hard to think that the medieval constructors of the great cathedrals did not aspire to eliciting a response of awe and wonder at experiencing the expansive vaulted spaces they created. Le Corbusier saw architecture as a matter of the heart, that it should produce a sense of well-being and appreciation of magnificence in the human ability to change their world. Asplund,

in his design for the law courts in Gothenberg (just as one instance), wanted to calm the nerves of the accused by making the pitch of the stairs to the upper floor, where the courts are situated, gentle. Even Frank Gehry, whose works are generally sculptural in nature, apparently wishes to elicit a sense of amazement in the twisted complexity of his titanium clad Bilbao Guggenheim Art Museum.

These emotional responses may not be as complex and subtle as those elicited by the powerful medium of music. Perhaps we would find it uncomfortable to be provoked into strong emotional responses to the places we occupy everyday in our domestic and work lives. But the emotional potential of architectural space, of place, is clearly evident, and might be put forward as a clear objective in architectural design, one that is often ignored but should be brought to the fore.

The challenge then is for architects to study the emotional power of architecture, and to be able find and exploit ways to control its effects in subtle and benevolent ways, for the increased enjoyment and comfort of daily life.

Coda

The students involved in the project went on to design buildings that had a potential emotional content. One went on to design a school and residential unit for autistic children; another designed a spa, with many sensual experiences; another explored the possibilities of architecture and dance; and another a centre for peace and meditation.... In all the sense of the emotional possibilities of architecture was more pronounced, though the difficulty of expressing this through the abstract media of drawing, scale models and computer graphics remained. The power of the work would only come to full appreciation if the buildings were constructed in reality, but hopefully that appreciation the students have acquired of the emotional potential of architecture will come out in the future design work, that which is realised.